

IMPROVING THE TEACHING METHODS OF LIFE SAFETY BASICS**Jolibekova Maryash Risnazarovna**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10473286>

Abstract. *The article explores the possibilities of the course “Methods of teaching and educating life safety” in the methodological preparation of a future teacher of the fundamentals of life safety in accordance with new standards.*

Keywords: *methodological training, independent work, research skills ,professional competence, informatization of the educational process.*

INTRODUCTION

Sociocultural demands and development trends of modern society determine the need to form a new type of teacher, possessing creative potential, striving for self-development, capable of identifying and creating conditions for the creative self-realization of the younger generation. The concept of modernizing Uzbek education requires the preparation of a qualitatively new teacher in the field of life safety, ready to work in new conditions, capable of adapting to the pedagogical innovations of a modern school. In the context of the implementation of new generation standards, one can note the key role of the course “Methods of teaching and upbringing life safety” in the professional methodological training of bachelors. Methodological training, being an important part of the professional training of bachelors, has its own goals and objectives, content, methods and pedagogical technologies, means and forms of organizing student training. Improving the methodological training of bachelors in the field of life safety is associated with studying a new course, which differs significantly from the previous one.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

When developing the course “Methods of training and education for life safety,” an analysis of the objectives and capabilities of this course was carried out, and its fundamental distinctive features from the previous course were taken into account. The content of the previous course on life safety methods was based on students acquiring certain knowledge, skills and abilities, and the modern course was developed taking into account the competency-based approach. Professional competence acts as an integrative characteristic that determines a graduate’s ability to solve professional problems using knowledge and experience [1,2,3]. Methodological competence can be considered as an important component of the professional competence of bachelors in the field of life safety, which is the result of methodological training and is expressed in the ability and readiness to effectively perform all types of methodological activities. Methodological competence corresponds to the main types of methodological activities of the future life safety teacher: design, organizational, communicative, gnostic, research, integrative and reflective.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In connection with the new requirements, the practical orientation of the course “Methods of training and education in life safety” was strengthened. The study of this course is based on a combination of lectures and laboratory classes, it should be noted that most of the allotted time is spent on laboratory work, the purpose of which is to develop in students the ability to design, organize the educational process, and anticipate its results. Therefore, the topics of laboratory

classes in the course are wide and varied: “Analysis of BLS (Basics of life safety) teaching methods”, “Methods of working with a textbook in a BLS lesson”, “Methodology for testing and monitoring students’ knowledge in BLS”, “Methodological requirements for organizing project-based learning in BLS lessons”, BLS Leading Learning Technologies and many more. In laboratory classes, students develop lesson fragments using a variety of teaching methods and techniques; compose different types of tasks to test and control knowledge; discuss possible types of homework by topic. Getting acquainted with the variety of technologies for teaching life safety, students identify the possibilities of using these technologies to solve professional problems in the classroom, learn to evaluate, select and adequately use them [4].

A characteristic feature of the preparation of a modern bachelor is the increased role of independent activity in the process of studying the course “Methods of teaching and educating life safety.” Independent work helps deepen and expand students' knowledge, develop interest in cognitive activity, and develop cognitive abilities. Strengthening the independent work of students is associated with the transition from the teaching paradigm to the learning paradigm [5, 6, 7]. Independent work of students is understood as a type of educational and cognitive activity for mastering a professional educational program, which has the following characteristics: the presence of a cognitive and practical task; manifestation of consciousness, independence and activity of students in the process of solving the task; availability of results. Independent work is considered not only as a form of learning, but also as a means of involving students in independent cognitive activity. The purpose of students’ independent work in the course “Methods of teaching and promoting life safety” is to motivate them to master the curriculum and increase responsibility for their studies. During the learning process, students are offered types of independent work that require different levels of independence.

Independent work of students when studying this course is one of the conditions for increasing the effectiveness of bachelor's training. The independent work offered to students is varied: work with sources, educational and scientific publications; working with reference materials; working with Internet sources; design; solving professional methodological problems. Students analyze the development of BLS concepts in different grades of a secondary school; identify the content and scope of skills in the BLS course; write a review of a BLS textbook (optional); complete a BLS field trip project; develop detailed lesson notes on BLS; designing an elective course on BLS, etc.

This course is also aimed at developing students' research skills. Research activity is one of the types of activities of the future teacher in BLS, its goal is the knowledge and transformation of pedagogical reality based on the achievements of pedagogical science and the application of scientific methods [8]. The future teacher must have research skills: the ability to navigate the flow of scientific information; mastering new teaching technologies; evaluating and selecting alternative and variable programs and creating your own original programs based on them.

Students are offered tasks on selecting literature on the topic, reading excerpts from methodological literature with critical analysis of the text. As a result, students acquire the ability to work with primary sources, independently find and analyze information. An important role in the formation of research skills is played by the implementation of projects.

In laboratory classes, students conduct a comparative analysis of school programs for the BLS course; write an essay on one of the BLS educational topics.

One of the priority areas of modernization of Russian education is the informatization of the educational process. Informatization of education is considered as a process of providing the education sector with the theory and practice of developing and using modern technologies focused on the implementation of psychological and pedagogical goals of training and education. The introduction of information technology into the BLS learning process in a modern school requires the graduate to be able to use information resources; organize distance learning; maintain electronic documents; carry out computer monitoring; develop online lessons.

The main goals of training teachers in BLS in the field of informatization of education are: developing ideas about the role of computerization of education, types of information technologies and methods of their application; studying the experience of using information technologies according to BLS; development of information culture; familiarization with the positive and negative aspects of the use of information technology in education. Based on the goals of informatization of education, lectures and practical classes of the course “Methods of teaching and educating life safety” were planned and developed. During the course lectures, students become familiar with methodological approaches to informatization of education; with Internet technologies of the educational process for BLS; with the concepts of “information environment”, “information culture”. Laboratory classes on this topic are based on the idea of informatization of education as a scientific and practical activity aimed at the use of computer technologies, collection, storage, processing and dissemination of information that ensures the systematization of knowledge. Students get acquainted with the methodology of using such ICT tools as an interactive whiteboard, electronic tools for teaching and educational purposes in BLS lessons; electronic textbooks; educational resources on the Internet; electronic libraries; virtual museums and exhibitions.

An active learning method, the use of which will be effective in life safety lessons - the **method of developing projects**, or project activities.

As pedagogical practice shows, the use of the project activity method allows students to develop the necessary research, communication and information skills. The project method is aimed at developing students' meta-subject skills and universal ways of working.

This method is focused on the creative self-realization of the student's personality in the process of students working on a project.

The next active learning method is **brainstorming**. This is one of the most effective ways to develop new and fresh ideas to solve a problem situation. The main goal of this method is to organize collective mental activity to find non-standard and creative ways to resolve problem situations. The use of this method in the educational process can help solve the following tasks:

- mastering lesson material using a creative approach;
- ensures the application of existing knowledge in practice;
- increasing motivation, stimulation and activation of the educational process;
- developing students' ability to focus all their attention and efforts on solving a given problem;
- accumulation of experience working in a team.

Another active learning method is **collective creative activity**. This is one of the effective methods of the educational process, which is based on positive production activity, group authorship, as well as a positive working atmosphere.

The next active learning method is a **round table**. This is another way to organize the educational process of students, which allows them to consolidate existing knowledge, refresh information in their memory, and also develops the ability to creatively solve identified problems, and ultimately gain the necessary useful experience of conducting a discussion in the classroom. The combination of discussion on a given topic and group consultation distinguishes this active learning method from other similar ones. In the process of learning using this technology, the student develops the ability to correctly express his thoughts, argue for them, as well as justify and defend his ideas.

Thus, by using active learning methods in his lessons, the life safety teacher promotes the development of thinking in students; involves them in solving problems that are as significant and close to real conditions as possible; It also helps to expand and deepen theoretical knowledge and finally helps to develop the necessary skills and abilities to act in specific situations.

Based on what was said earlier, the use of these methods certainly activates the educational process, encourages students to actively and creatively participate in it, and finally allows the student's personality to comprehensively develop and self-improvement, taking into account his individual creative, psychological, social, emotional, and so on characteristics and abilities.

The development and application of effective technologies and teaching methods, new forms of organizing the educational process, the formation of new relationships is the requirement of the time today. With the systematic and harmattan application of active methods, the role of the teacher changes significantly. He becomes a mentor, a senior comrade, which radically changes the attitude of the students towards him; the teacher turns into a more experienced comrade, playing on the same team with the students.

CONCLUSION

The course "Methods of teaching and educating life safety" is compiled in the field of life safety in the direction of "Pedagogical Education" and is focused on training a teacher-researcher with the following competencies:

- ability to apply modern methods and technologies for organizing and implementing the educational process;
- readiness to develop and implement methodological models, methods, technologies and teaching methods in the subject area of life safety;
- the ability to use modern technologies in creating a safe environment in an educational institution;
- willingness to design new educational content, technologies and specific teaching methods in the field of life safety education.

Thus, when selecting the content of the course "Methods of training and education for life safety," the following trends in education were taken into account:

- strengthening the practical orientation of the course;
- the leading role of students' independent work;
- development of students' research skills;
- informatization of the educational process.

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